

Effect of organic and inorganic nitrogen on growth of nursery (mean of 1981 and 1982), Ludhiana, India.

Treatment		Dry matter (mg/plant)	Leaves/plant	Plant ht (cm)	Color index ^a (A)	Seedling strength (mg/cm) (B)	Seedling quality (A × B)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N (kg/ha)	Organic N							
0	–	76	6	18	1	4	4	–
60	–	152	8	25	2	6	12	5.6
120	–	212	9	30	3	7	22	6.6
60	Farmyard manure	153	8	27	2	6	11	5.5
60	Poultry manure	169	8	32	3	5	16	–
60	Green manure	215	8	28	3	8	24	6.5
60	Azolla	174	7	26	2	7	14	–

^a1 = pale yellow, 3 = dark green.

N, P, K, S, Fe, Mn, Zn, and Cu in treatments receiving 60 kg N/ha and dhaincha green manure was higher than with 60 kg N alone and equaled that of 120 kg N. Nursery treatments that received 120 kg N/ha and green manure + 60 kg N/ha yielded significantly more grain than other treatments (see table). □

Individuals, organizations, and media who want additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

Influence of phosphorus and pyrite on azolla growth

S. Venkataraman and S. Kannaiyan, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the effect of superphosphate (SSP), Mussorie rock phosphate (MRP), and pyrite on azolla growth in pot culture. Treatments were SSP alone, MRP alone, SSP and pyrite, MRP and pyrite, at 0, 5, 10, 15, and 20 kg P/ha. Azolla at 200 g/m² was inoculated and 20 ppm carbofuran was applied. Azolla

Influence of phosphorus (P), Mussorie rock phosphate (MRP) and pyrite on azolla growth, Tamil Nadu, India.

P (kg/ha)	SSP		SSP + pyrite		MRP		MRP' + pyrite	
	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control	Mean azolla wt (g)	% increase over control
Control (0)	90.0	–	111	–	101	–	100	–
5	129.0	43	138	24	108	6	133	32
10	142.0	58	146	31	114	13	141	41
15	151.5	68	157	41	120	19	153	52
20	166.0	84	177	59	120	19	159	59
LSD (P = 0.05)			LSD: 6.284	LSD: 8.019	LSD: 8.010		LSD: 5.824	

fresh weight was recorded 10 d after inoculation.

All P treatments increased azolla

growth over that of the control (see table). Results indicate that MRP + pyrite is superior for azolla growth. □

Azolla as a substitute for fertilizer

N. Haq, and D. Rosh, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Mingora (Swat); and P. Shah, NWFP Agricultural University, Peshawar, Pakistan

We sought to determine how much N fertilizer can be saved by growing azolla, using J.P.5 rice at ARS in Mingora in 1982. The station is at 35°N latitude and at 975 m altitude. Climate is cool and irrigation water is 15°C.

Azolla treatments, similar to those adopted for 1981-82 INSFFER trials (see table), were in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications in 5- × 3-m plots. Plant height, tillers/hill, and grain yield were recorded and statistically analyzed.

Yield with azolla culture was similar to that with 60 kg applied N/ha (see table). We found that azolla culture has a

Rice yield and other data from azolla experiments at ARS, Mingora (Swat), Peshawar, Pakistan.

Treatment (N/ha)	Panicles/hill	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0 N, 0 azolla, 20- × 20-cm spacing	6	98	3.2
60 kg N, 20- × 20-cm spacing	7	98	3.7
60 kg N, 40- × 10-cm spacing	8	105	4.8
Azolla incorporation before transplanting, 30 kg N, 20- × 20-cm spacing	8	100	3.8
Azolla incorporation before transplanting, 30 kg N, 40- × 10-cm spacing	9	110	5.0
Azolla grown once before and once after transplanting and incorporated, 20- × 20-cm spacing	6	100	4.1
Azolla grown once before and once after transplanting and incorporated, 40- × 10-cm spacing	8	101	4.5
Azolla grown twice after transplanting, 40- × 10-cm spacing	8	101	4.7
90 kg N as urea in 3 splits, 0 azolla, 20- × 20-cm spacing	9	105	4.7
90 kg N as urea in 3 splits, 0 azolla, 40- × 10-cm spacing	9	105	5.5

beneficial effect on soil structure, soil microflora, and micronutrient availability. The azolla effect may persist longer than

N fertilizers on subsequent crops and its effect may increase over time to surpass those of commercial N fertilizers. □